

M.Sc thesis

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Assessed rates of fisheries induced evolution are affected by the type of density dependence

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$$f(x+\Delta x) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\Delta x)^i}{i!} f^{(i)}(x)$$
$$\Delta \int_a^b \varepsilon \Theta + \Omega \int \delta e^{i\pi} =$$
$$\infty = \{2.7182818284\}$$
$$\chi^2 \sum ! \gg \approx$$

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Material and methods	5
2.1	Consumption	5
2.2	Energy allocation	7
2.3	Mortality	8
2.4	Spectrum	10
2.5	Density dependence	11
2.6	Evolutionary impact assessment	13
3	Results	18
3.1	Effect of density dependence on the population	18
3.2	Effect of density dependence on the fishing selection response	19
4	Discussion	22
5	Conclusion	24

1 Introduction

Fish populate all the world's oceans, from the surface (pelagic) to the abyss (benthic), as well as fresh water. The high productivity of fish stock makes them an important source of food for humans, for instance, FAO (2018) has estimated that despite the increasing fish production from aquaculture, fishing from marine and lakes provide about 12% of the global animal protein consumption. Studying fisheries is therefore of interest for various fields and has become multidisciplinary, with contribution from anthropologists, human geographers, politicians, theoretical-economists (Clark and Munro, 1975), and last but not least, biologist-ecologist-mathematicians (Volterra, 1926). ()

Before developing fishing, its history and its implications more deeply, it is of importance to provide an appropriate definition. The term fishing usually defines the activity of catching mainly fish and molluscs, it is not normally applied to catching farmed fish, or to aquatic mammals, such as whales. Fish populations are valuable resources beget by their generous productivity, and were consequently used since the dawn of time. The beginning of the industrial area caused a complete change to the structure of fisheries, which turned to an industrial scale. The beginning of mechanisation with the appearance of the steam engine and the development of railroads, used to transport fish from ports, caused an increase of fishing in Europe around 1850. During the 20st century, mechanisation has produced enormous trawls, capable to exploit offshore fish stocks for long periods by freezing harvested fish (Sahrhage and Lundbeck, 1992). These innovations have led to overfishing during the last recent years, with strong ecological and economical issues.

Efforts were made to understand why fishing is increasing while fish resources are declining. An answer could be found through a well-known process called 'the tragedy of the commons', indeed, fish populations are the perfect example of common property, which are currently declining. The theory has been developed by Hardin (1968) in order to show that the problem of human overpopulation cannot be solved by technology (i.e., increasing the resource). Stillman (1975) stressed that three assumptions must be fulfilled for the tragedy to occur: users should be selfish; the environment must be limited; and the resource must be open to any user and collectively owned by society. The theory has been transposed to fish resources (Berkes, 1985). Consider a limited system with a limited fish production that fishermen are exploiting. The theory is founded on the principle that the cost of increasing

fishing is shared over the community, but the gain is individually earned. Assuming that a fisherman adds a new boat in the system, his individual additional gain is, for instance, +1, and the common cost is -1. In that situation, and considering that each fisherman is selfish, the only reasonable strategy is to increasing your number of boat in the system. That is the ineluctable tragedy leading to a depletion of the resource and a fall of the individual fisherman catches per fishing effort. A consequent question of interest addressed by Berkes (1985) is ‘can communities of fishermen self-regulate their fishing effort?’. Social regulation, introduction of quotas by cooperatives, or governmental restrictions were found out to be ways to control fishing, and reduce its consequences.

Historically, first studies about fish populations highlight the population demography, and the loss of yield due to overexploitation. Fisheries, however, does not only impact demography, it also exerts a selection pressure which leads to an evolutionary response (Jorgensen et al., 2007). Indeed, overfishing induced high mortality on fish populations (Mertz and Myers, 1998), which is generally size selective. Life history theory predicts that an increase of mortality, on specific phenotype characteristics, such as body size, induced evolution. Body size is a state instead of a trait, the selection on size is therefore an indirect selection on traits, such as maturation size and growth rate. Generally, a such evolution leads, for fish populations, to faster life history traits such as: earliest size at maturation, increasing reproduction effort, and increasing metabolism (Heino and God, 2002; Law, 2000). Evolution of life history traits begets an obvious response at the population scale, such as, stock biomass depletion, decreasing of the population sustainability, economic issues (Law and Grey, 1989; Conover, 2002), and slower stocks recovery (Walsh et al., 2006). Such an evolution has been observed through experimentation (Walsh et al., 2006), but fishing induced evolution assessment on natural populations is facing a problem, how to distinguish true evolution and phenotype plasticity?

Such an answer is provided by modelling fish population, which required a relevant way to represent the fish community. In fish science, a common representation of the community is obtained by considering the body size of all individuals. Elton (1926) had already pointed out the importance of size in trophic food-webs, and gives the early stages of relations between prey and predator sizes. The precise representation through size of marine community

had to wait until Sheldon works became wildly popular in the field. He shown that biomass inside a size range is roughly constant, and that this pattern is repeated from bacteria to whales (Sheldon et al., 1972; Sheldon and Parsons, 1967) with a decline of biomass for large individuals. The Sheldon spectrum is nothing more than the pyramid of Elton for marine ecosystems. The sheldon spectrum theory has inspired models to describe fish population such as the Von Bertalanffy growth model. These kind of models have been used to calculated fishing induced evolution (Andersen and Brander, 2009).

However, a complication in quantitative genetics calculations on fish stocks is the issue of density dependence. Natural populations are regulated by increasing their density through variation of growth and mortality. In marine fish populations, density dependence was commonly modelled through a stock-recruitment function, regulating the number of new offsprings with increasing adult biomass (Beverton and Holt, 1957). These models assumed that density dependence only occurs at the beginning of life, at least before fishing. Empirical evidences contrast this assumption, showing that density dependence also occurs later in life through a reduction of growth rate (Graham, 1948; Lorenzen and Enberg, 2002) or through cannibalism from larger individuals (Smith and Reay, 1991). Some fishing induced evolution assessment does represent both early-life density dependence and dependent changes growth (Eikeset et al., 2016; Vainikka and Hyvärinen, 2012), but they do so only with a heuristic linear change in growth with population size. Currently, there is a lack of theoretical knowledge about how density dependence affects fishing induced evolution, and what kind of density dependence should be considered. The aim of the project is to understand how the kind of density dependence affects fishing induced evolution assessment. Specifically, I wanted to understand how much it matters that most fishing induced evolution calculations ignore density dependent growth and cannibalism. In other words: are the current state-of-the-art calculations good enough, or do they do a systematic error by ignoring density dependent growth and cannibalism?

To that end I employed a size-based model of fish populations, developed by Andersen and Beyer (2015), considering three kinds of density dependence: early-life density dependence through a stock-recruitment relationship, competition associated with a reduction of individual growth rate, and cannibalism which occurs as a mortality induced by large individuals

in the populations. This model does not impose a reduction of growth rate or an increasing mortality, but density dependence effects emerge from the model dynamic. The species is considered through a single trait, the asymptotic size. A problem with this model is that it is a dynamic consumer-resource model. In contrast to the usual demographic models, it is not straight-forward to use quantitative genetics to calculate selection responses. I therefore developed a method where I used a resident-invader approach (Brännström et al., 2013), inspired by adaptive dynamics to calculate fishing induced evolution.

In the following I first introduce the size based model, and evolutionary calculations. In order to better understand evolutionary calculation, I first describe the effect of the type of density dependence on the population. I secondly developed how density dependence effect evolutionary calculation for increasing fishing intensity and asymptotic size.

2 Material and methods

Fishing-induced evolution was assessed through a size-based model developed by Andersen et al. (2017) (see also Andersen and Beyer (2015)). Body size w is the base of the model and refers wet weight and is described in grams. Here, a single population is considered separately from the rest of the community, called the resource. Individuals in the population eat resource (predation), and smaller individuals in the population (cannibalism). This model is based on an energy-budget model in which individuals obtain energy, from the resource and from other individuals in the population, which is allocated to growth and reproduction. The cannibalism appears from the predation on the population itself, and the competition emerges from the resource limitation. The model described below is based on asymptotic size as a fish trait, describing different species. Model coefficients and equations are summarised in Tab. 1 and appendix A, respectively.

2.1 Consumption

Individuals use energy for reproduction, growth and to maintain basic metabolic functions. This energy is gained by a predation mechanism. The predators ability to catch a prey can be described by three quantities: the prey size preference of the predator ϕ , the clearance rate V , and the maximum consumption rate C_{\max} .

Predators are not able to eat all individuals in the environment. Generally, predators prefer to eat preys smaller than themselves, but this preference is driven by two conditions. The energy gained to catch small prey is lower than the cost of the capture, and the benefit of large prey is lower than the effort. On that basis, Ursin (1973) described the size preference for a predator of size w and a prey of size w_p (without unit), through the function:

$$\phi(w, w_p) = \exp \left[\frac{-(\ln(w/(\beta w_p)))^2}{2\sigma^2} \right], \quad (1)$$

where, β is the preferred predator:prey mass ratio and σ is the width of the function. The maximum preference is reached when the predator:prey mass ratio is equal to β (Fig. 1A).

The available energy contained in the system for predators in the population is determined by the resource spectrum N_{res} (from predation) and by the population spectrum N (from cannibalism; units of numbers per mass per volume). The available food E (mass per volume) can be described as the integral over the biomass spectrum of prey in the system $N(w_p)w_p$ (resource and population) of a given prey size w_p , weighted by the preference for size:

$$E(w) = \int_0^\infty (N_{\text{res}}(w_p) + N(w_p))w_p\phi(w_p/w)dw_p. \quad (2)$$

Predator encounter prey by actively searching or by waiting for it. The food encountered is therefore limited by the actual volume covered by the predator. We defined an encounter rate which describes the fraction of prey encountered by the predator regarding to its size. The equation is inspired by the clearance rate V , describing the volume of water cleared by filterers of size w : $V(w) = \gamma w^q$. It has been asserted that the same relation can describe the encounter rate for fish (Andersen and Beyer, 2006). For fish, the clearance rate (volume per time) is the encounter rate of organisms (numbers per time) divided by the concentration of prey (numbers per volume). The actual food encountered E_e (mass per time) for a predator can be now simply described as the available food in the system weighted by the clearance rate:

$$E_e(w) = V(w)E(w). \quad (3)$$

Food consumption of fish is limited by their maximum digestive capacity. West (1997) proposed that gut surface scales the body size of individuals with an exponent of 3/4. Then

the maximum consumption rate (mass per time) is described as:

$$C_{\max}(w) = h \cdot w^n, \quad (4)$$

with $n = 3/4$ the metabolic exponent and h the coefficient for maximum consumption. Consequently, if the food encountered is higher than an individual can maximally consume, then the food encountered is not entirely used. The actual consumption rate C (units of mass per time) is defined as the maximum consumption (i.e., C_{\max}) weighted by the feeding level. The feeding level of an individual is described through a predation function response of type II (Holling, 1959):

$$f(w) = \frac{E_e(w)}{E_e(w) + hw^n}, \quad (5)$$

which varies from 0 to 1, without unit. The predator consumption is then : $C(w) = f(w)C_{\max}(w)$. When the food is rare ($E_e \ll C_{\max}$), all the encounter food is consumed ($C \approx E_e$), and when the food is abundant ($E_e \gg C_{\max}$), not all the food encountered is consumed ($C \approx C_{\max}$).

2.2 Energy allocation

The energy extracted by a predator from the environment is allocated to various process such as growth, reproduction, standard metabolism and activity. The available energy E_a (mass per time) used for growth and reproduction is defined as:

$$E_a(w) = \epsilon_a(f(w) - f_c)hw^n, \quad (6)$$

where $f(w)$ is the feeding level, f_c is the critical feeding level describing the fraction of energy used to maintain the basic metabolic function, and ϵ_a is the assimilation coefficient used to represent the fraction of energy lost during the assimilation process. Coefficient f_c and ϵ_a are unitless.

The fraction of the available energy allocated to growth or reproduction is determined by a maturation function:

$$\Psi(w) = [1 + (w/(\eta W_\infty))^{-u}]^{-1}. \quad (7)$$

Juveniles invest all energy in growth, when they reach the maturation size w_m they gradually

start investing in reproduction and less in growth (Fig. 1B). The size at maturation is calculated from the asymptotic size W_∞ (size at which an individual invest only in reproduction and no more in growth) by the following relation: $w_m = \eta_m W_\infty$. Growth and reproduction are both described as an energy (mass per time) as:

$$g(w) = E_a(w) \left[1 - \Psi(w/w_m) \left(\frac{w}{W_\infty} \right)^{(1-n)} \right], \quad (8)$$

$$R_{\text{egg}}(w) = \epsilon_{\text{egg}} E_a(w) \Psi(w/w_m) \left(\frac{w}{W_\infty} \right)^{(1-n)}. \quad (9)$$

The growth is defined as the available energy E_a subtracted to the energy used for reproduction (Fig. 1B). The number of eggs produced at a size w is the energy invested in reproduction weighed by a coefficient of conversion efficiency from food to eggs ϵ_{egg} .

The total egg production, also called reproductive output R_p (number per time), is given by integrating over size the number of eggs produced by the population:

$$R_p = \frac{\epsilon_R}{w_0} \int_{w_0}^{W_\infty} R_{\text{egg}}(w) N(w) dw, \quad (10)$$

where ϵ_R is the recruitment efficiency. A stock-recruitment relation was included (Beverton and Holt, 1957) describing how early-life density dependence reduces the recruitment from eggs production in the population:

$$R = R_{\text{max}} \frac{R_p}{R_p + R_{\text{max}}}, \quad (11)$$

where, R is the number of offspring (number per time), R_p the reproductive output, and R_{max} is the maximum recruitment (i.e., $\lim_{R_p \rightarrow +\infty} R = R_{\text{max}}$). This relation introduces a reduction of the reproduction early in life, due to density dependence.

2.3 Mortality

In the resource-consumer model the mortality is decomposed into three types, which arises from three distinct sources: the background mortality μ_b , the predation mortality μ_p , and the fishing mortality μ_F . The total mortality μ (per time) inflicted to individuals in the

Figure 1: THE CONSUMER RESOURCE MODEL. A) The predator-prey size preference function (Eq. 1) over prey:predator mass ratio w/w_p . B) The functions of growth (Eq. 8) and maturation (Eq. 7) related to the size at maturation (w_m , represented by the vertical dotted-line). C) The background mortality (Eq. 13; blue dotted-line), the fishing mortality (Eq. 15; orange line) and the total mortality (Eq. 12; blue dashed line) are represented. The difference between the background mortality and total mortality depict, for small size, the effect of cannibalism by larger individuals, and for large size the effect of fishing. The maximum fishing mortality F was fixed at 0.3. D) The population spectrum (Eq. 16; orange line) and the resource spectrum (Eq. 17; blue line) were calculated for a population with asymptotic size W_∞ of 1000 g, and with a resource regeneration factor r_0 of $4 \text{ g}^{1-n} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. All other coefficients are describe in Tab. 1.

population is merely the sum of the three types of mortality named above:

$$\mu(w) = \mu_b(w) + \mu_p(w) + \mu_F(w). \quad (12)$$

The background mortality arises from other large fish in the environment, in other words it is the mortality induced by the resource spectrum. This mortality scales with the individual body size with a power law of exponent $n - 1$ (Brown et al., 2004), therefore the mortality decreases with the body size as:

$$\mu_b(w) = \mu_0 w^{n-1}. \quad (13)$$

The predation inflicted to small individuals from larger individuals in the population itself is calculated such that it exactly mirrors the amount of biomass consumed. In this way the model balances the mass used for growth and reproduction of predators with a corresponding death of prey:

$$\mu_p(w_p) = \int_0^\infty \phi(w_p/w)(1 - f(w))\gamma w^q N(w)dw. \quad (14)$$

Fishing practices are diverse and select fish within specific size range such as grill net, trawl, or trap. For the sake of simplicity only trawl fishing was considered in this model, mainly because it is a dominant fishing practice.

$$\mu_F(w) = F\psi_F(w). \quad (15)$$

The selectivity of a trawl gear is described by a sigmoidal function: $\psi_{\text{trawl}} = (1+(w/(\eta_F w_\infty))^{-u_0})^{-1}$, where $\eta_F w_\infty$ is the size at which the selectivity is equal to 0.5, meaning that 50% of the maximum fishing mortality is reached at this size. The size at 50% fishing $\eta_F w_\infty$ was supposed to be lower than w_m , assuming firstly that both mature and juvenile fish are harvested, and secondly that w_m and $\eta_F w_\infty$ are independent. It is important to distinguish fisheries targeting only mature individuals and fisheries targeting both matures and juveniles, since they induce different kinds of selection response (Dunlop et al., 2009).

2.4 Spectrum

The growth and mortality, expressed above, describe how individuals in the population change in size and time. In a small size range $[w, w+dw]$ individuals grow or die. On that basis the conservation equation of McKendrick-von Forester allows to describe the continuous population size spectrum:

$$\frac{\partial N(w)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial g(w)N(w)}{\partial w} = -\mu(w)N(w). \quad (16)$$

The left-hand-side expresses conservation of numbers as organisms grow in size and the right-hand-side is losses to mortality. This equation has to be solved, since all equations depend on the size spectrum. The numerical method to solve Eq. 16 was developed by Andersen et al. (2016) and is presented in appendix B.

Other organisms in the community, that the fish can feed on, is represented by a resource spectrum. This spectrum can represent various kind of food from small zooplankton to other fish. The resource is here modelled dynamically with the chemostat dynamics:

$$\frac{dN_{\text{res}}(w)}{dt} = r_0 w^{n-1} (k_{\text{res}}(w) - N_{\text{res}}(w)) - \mu_{\text{p}}(w) N_{\text{res}}(w). \quad (17)$$

The population growth rate $r_0 w^{n-1}$ scales with the metabolic exponent to body size. The procedure of discretization is the same as explained for the population spectrum (appendix B).

2.5 Density dependence

Density dependence affects individual growth rate, mortality and reproduction. To evaluate the effect of each kind of density dependence on fishing induced evolution, they have to be controlled and measured. Three types of density dependence operate: early-life density dependence, cannibalism, and competition. The early-life density dependence is imposed as an external process, while the cannibalism and competition are emerging phenomena in the model.

Early-life density dependence is given by the stock-recruitment function (Eq. 11), which imposes a progressive limitation of the amount of new offspring with increasing reproductive output (Eq. 10). The level of early-life density dependence is controlled by the maximum recruitment R_{max} (e.g., increasing R_{max} reduces the strength of early-life density dependence, see Fig. 2A, solid blue line).

The strength of competition depends on the relation between the resource and the density of individuals in the population, therefore, the level of resource can be increased or decreased by respectively increasing or decreasing r_0 . In the case of low resource (i.e., low r_0) and low early-life density dependence (i.e., high R_{max}), the competition is maximised (Fig. 2A and B; blue area).

Cannibalism occurs through predation from large individuals on smaller ones and is therefore regulated by the population density and the resource. A high density of individuals (i.e., high r_0 and high R_{max}) leads to high cannibalism (Fig. 3A and B; orange area).

The strength of density dependence is evaluated differently for each type of density depen-

Figure 2: POPULATION DYNAMICS. A) The Sheldon spectrum of the resource (orange lines) and of the population (blue lines) for three types of density dependence. Early-life density dependence is characterised by a low density, the competition by a resource depletion, and the cannibalism by a reduction of middle-size spectrum. B) The feeding (Eq. 5) and losses (see Eq. 19) for each type of density dependence. Competition is characterised by a reduction in feeding level (around 10^2 g), and the cannibalism by an increasing mortality (around 10^0 g). The abbreviation DD represents "Density Dependence". Simulations were done with an asymptotic size of 1000 g, a fishing mortality of 0.3 years^{-1} , all other parameters are described in Tab. 1.

dence. Early-life density dependence is simply evaluated by the ratio between the number of eggs produced and the number of new offspring (i.e., R/R_p), and emerges as a reduction of the spectrum (Fig. 2A).

The strength of competition was calculated as a reduction in the feeding level f . The system was adjusted such that the feeding level is at a value of 0.6 when the resource is at the carrying capacity. Consequently, the effect of competition can be calculated as the integral of the difference between the constant function of value 0.6 and the actual feeding:

$$C_{\text{comp}} = \int_{w_0}^{w_\infty} 0.6(w_\infty - w_0) - f(w)dw, \quad (18)$$

with $f(w)$ the feeding of the population (see Fig. 2B, dashed blue line, and competition area).

The strength of cannibalism was evaluated by calculating the predation suffered by the population from the population itself. The losses due to cannibalism in the population can be described as the ratio between predation mortality from the population and weight-

specific maximum consumption (see Fig. 2B, orange dotted line, cannibalism orange area). Integrating the losses of cannibalism over size, the cannibalism effect is evaluated:

$$C_{\text{can}} = \int_{w_0}^{w_\infty} \frac{\mu_p}{hw^{n-1}} dw. \quad (19)$$

The competition and cannibalism effects (i.e., respectively C_{comp} and C_{can}) were calculated for varying values of r_0 and R_{max} (Fig. 3A and B). The cannibalism is maximised for r_0 and R_{max} values of respectively 10 and $4.10^{-4} \text{ g}^{1-n} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3A); the maximum competition is reached for r_0 and R_{max} values of respectively 0.1 and $4.10^{-4} \text{ g}^{1-n} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3B); and the early-life density dependence is maximised for a low R_{max} of $4.10^{-8} \text{ g}^{1-n} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. For the following, the three kinds of density dependence were distinguished and the parameters are fixed as above (see Tab. 1). Competition and cannibalism effects are maintained over maximum fishing, F and asymptotic size, W_∞ (Fig. 3C, D, E, and F). Strength of cannibalism or cannibalism are relatively low for systems driven by respectively early-life density dependence and competition or early-life density dependence and cannibalism.

2.6 Evolutionary impact assessment

In this study, fishing-induced evolution assessment on the size at maturation (w_m) was done through an invasion-resident approach. This approach assumes the separation of time scales. Ecological time scale is shorter than evolution time scale, then evolution is assumed to occur only when ecological systems are stable. The population spectrum and its environment were therefore simulated until stability (i.e., $N(w, t) \approx N(w, t + 1)$). Then, an invader population, with a specific size at maturation, was considered separately from the resident population, assuming that its density is low comparatively to the resident density (i.e., $N_{\text{res}} \ll N$). First, the variation of invader biomass for a specific size at maturation was calculated over time in order to extract an invader population growth rate. Secondly, the derivative of invader growth rates was calculated over a small variation of size at maturation (i.e., varying from the initial condition w_m to $w_m(1 + \Delta_m)$, with $\Delta_m = 0.02$). Finally, the selection response on size at maturation was evaluated over increasing fishing F , and asymptotic size W_∞ .

The invader environment such as cannibalism, resource, and recruitment, were defined by the population. The cannibalism suffered by the invaders is only imposed by the resident

Figure 3: ASSESSMENT OF THE LEVEL OF DENSITY DEPENDENCE. A) and B) The level of both cannibalism and competition were estimated for r_0 and R_{max} ranging respectively from 0.1 to 10 g¹⁻ⁿ yr⁻¹ and from 4.10⁻⁸ to 4.10⁻⁴ nbr. yr⁻¹. C) to F) Level of cannibalism and competition for each type of density dependence (1. Early-life density dependence; 2. Competition; 3. Cannibalism). The parameters r_0 and R_{max} were fixed for each type of density dependence (see Tab. 1).

population, since invader density is low, the resulting cannibalism pressure from invaders is assumed to be null. The resource was partly consumed by the resident population, the rest of it is available for invaders. The available resource for invaders was calculated as the resource at the resident equilibrium. The model states that the number of offspring is limited by the stock-recruitment function Eq. 11, in other words, the reproduction is limited, and below a threshold (R_{max}). Consequently, the number of new offspring from invaders depends on the amount of offspring produced by residents. The stock-recruitment function (Eq. 11) states that R_p is reduced by a coefficient ($R_{max}/(R_{p, resd} + R_{max})$) depending on R_p . This stock reduction coefficient was extract from the resident stock-recruitment relation and was applied as a reduction factor to the invaders reproductive output $R_{p, ivd}$, to take into account of resident offspring reduction:

$$R_{ivd} = R_{p, ivd} \frac{R_{max}}{R_{p, resd} + R_{max}}, \quad (20)$$

where, R_{ivd} is the number of new offspring from the resident population, and $R_{\text{p, resd}}$ is the egg production from the resident population. The growth rate of the invader population r_{ivd} , was calculated through the following equation:

$$\frac{dB_{\text{SSB}}}{dt} = r_{\text{ivd}}B_{\text{SSB}}, \quad (21)$$

where, B_{SSB} is the spawning stock biomass of invaders (i.e., the biomass of mature individuals), calculated as the integral over body size of the biomass spectrum weighted by the function at maturation:

$$B_{\text{SSB}} = \int_{w_0}^{w_\infty} N(w)\phi(w)w dw \quad (22)$$

The solution of the differential equation gives: $r_{\text{ivd}} = \ln(B_{\text{SSB}}(t + \Delta_t)/B_{\text{SSB}}(t))\frac{1}{\Delta_t}$ expressed in units of time^{-1} . The simulated population biomass oscillates with a decreasing amplitude when the time is increasing. On long term simulations, the log of invader population biomass tends to a linear function (Fig. 4A). For the sake of the simplicity, the logarithm of the invader population biomass was considered as a linear function on long term:

$$\ln(B_{\text{SSB}}) = at + b, \quad (23)$$

with, B_{SSB} the biomass of mature individual in the population, a the slope of the linear function, and t the time in year. The invader population growth rate can now be solved as:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{\text{ivd}} &= [\ln(N(t + \Delta_t)) - \ln(N(t))]\frac{1}{\Delta_t} \\ &= [a(t + \Delta_t) + b - (at + b)]\frac{1}{\Delta_t} = a. \end{aligned}$$

The approach of the selection response, developed in this study, is inspired by the classic quantitative genetics equation. In this case instead consider a variation of fitness with the traits we consider a variation of invasion fitness of a theoretical invader population in a resident environment (Brännström et al., 2013). The selection response measures the variation of trait over time. Here the selection response on the size at maturation was assumed to be equal to the variation of invader growth rate over size at maturation divided by the resident size at maturation $w_{\text{m, res}}$, and weighted by the heritability h^2 , and the variation of the trait in the population $(Cv w_{\text{m}})^2$. Here it is assumed, as in quantitative genetics, that higher

Figure 4: INVADER-RESIDENT APPROACH. A) Biomass of mature invaders over time (B_{SSB}). The biomass of mature individual was calculated as the integral of the total biomass weighed by the maturation function. Calculation were done with and without fishing (respectively orange and blue lines), and for an invasion size at maturation equal or higher than that of the population (respectively dashed and solid lines). B) Invasion population growth rate for increasing size at maturation of invaders. Arrows represent the direction of evolution evaluated at the size at the resident maturation size.

heritability and higher trait variation in the population increase the selection response:

$$S = h^2(Cv w_{m, res})^2 \frac{1}{w_{m, res}} \left. \frac{dr}{dw_m} \right|_{w_m = w_{m, res}}. \quad (24)$$

The heritability was fixed at 0.2 and is without unit. The variation of the trait in the population is equal to the squared mean asymptotic size in the population weighed by a coefficient of variation Cv fixed at 0.2. In other words, the variation of the trait in the population is the variance of the trait and is of unit g^2 .

Fishing effect on invader population growth rate was calculated as the difference between the derivative of invader growth rate with and without fishing (Fig. 4B). Each derivative of invader growth rate were calculated as the variation in invader population growth rate

Table 1: Model parameters. Notation: var. refers to variable and nbr. to number.

Symbol	Description	Value	Unit	Reference
<i>Body size</i>				
w	Body size	var.	g	
W_∞	Asymptotic size	var.	g	
w_m	Size at maturation	var.	g	
w_0	Egg weight	10^{-3}	g	1
<i>Consumption</i>				
β	Preferred predator:prey mass ratio	408	-	2
σ	Width of prey size selection function	1	-	3
γ	Coefficient for clearance rate	$1.98e+03$	$g^{1-n} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	3
q	Clearance rate exponent	0.8	-	4
n	Coefficient of metabolic scale	3/4	-	5
h	Coefficient for maximum consumption	22.3	$g^{1-n} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	3
<i>Growth and Reproduction</i>				
ϵ_a	Assimilation efficiency	0.6	-	6
f_c	Critical feeding level	0.2	-	7
η_m	Coefficient of maturation related to W_∞	0.28	-	8, 9
u	Maturation function coefficient	5	-	
ϵ_{egg}	Conversion efficiency from food to eggs	0.22	-	10
ϵ_R	recruitment efficiency	0.03	-	
<i>Mortality</i>				
μ_0	Coefficient of physiological mortality	2.247		
F	Maximum fishing mortality	var.	yr^{-1}	
η_F	Coefficient 50% fishing related to W_∞	0.05	-	
u_0	Sharpness of the selection	3	$g^{1-n} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	
<i>Dynamics</i>				
k_{res0}	Resource carrying capacity	$5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	g^{-3-q+n}/m^3	
q	Resource scaling	0.8	-	
<i>Competition</i>				
r_0	Resource regeneration factor	0.1	$g^{1-n} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	
R_{max}	Max. recruitment	0.1	nbr. per time	
<i>Cannibalism</i>				
r_0	Resource regeneration factor	20	$g^{1-n} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	
R_{max}	Max. recruitment	$4.439e-4$	nbr. per time	
<i>Early-life density dependence</i>				
r_0	Resource regeneration factor	10	$g^{1-n} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	
R_{max}	Max. recruitment	$4.4394e-8$	nbr. per time	

¹ Neuheimer et al. (2015). ² Jennings et al. (2002). ³ Andersen et al. (2017). ⁴ Andersen et al. (2016). ⁵ West (1997) ⁶ Kitchell et al. (1977). ⁷ Hartvig et al. (2011). ⁸ Gunderson (1997). ⁹ Andersen and Beyer (2015). ¹⁰ Andersen et al. (2019).

divided by the variation in invader size at maturation:

$$\frac{dr}{dw_{m,ivd}} = \frac{r(w_{m,res}) - r(w_{m,ivd})}{w_{m,res} - w_{m,ivd}},$$

with $r(w_{m,res})$ the population growth rate of invaders for a resident size at maturation, $w_{m,ivd}/w_{m,res} = 0.02$ the variation rate of size at maturation. The derivative is calculated at the population size at maturation, meaning that evolutionary calculation were done at the starting point.

All the simulations and figures were realised with matlab 2018b, student version.

3 Results

3.1 Effect of density dependence on the population

Figure 5: POPULATION SPECTRUM UNDER HIGH VERSUS LOW FISHING. The Population spectrum (A) and the feeding and loss (B) are obtained for high ($F = 1$) and low ($F = 0.1$) fishing, and for the three types of density dependence. The population asymptotic size was fixed at 10^3 g, other parameters are described in Tab. 1. Light grey areas represent low fishing condition, and grey areas represent high fishing condition.

High fishing pressure induced a reduction of large individuals in the population for the three kinds of density dependence (Fig. 5A). However, the biomass reduction due to increasing

fishing is lower for the population driven by competition (Fig. 5A; difference between blue and orange dotted-lines) than populations driven by either early-life density dependence or cannibalism (Fig. 5A; difference between blue and orange full or dashed lines, respectively).

For the three kinds of density dependence the losses increase for large individuals (Fig. 5B; loss above 10^1 g), due to harvested fish. Increasing fishing is associated with higher feeding level for large individuals (Fig. 5B; feeding: light-grey and grey areas around 10^2 g) meaning that the strength of competition decreases with fishing. Similarly, high fishing pressure induced a reduction of loss at medium size (Fig. 5B; for loss: light-grey and grey areas around 10^0 g) meaning that the strength of cannibalism decreases with fishing.

Systems driven by early-life density dependence experiment an increasing of fishing effect with asymptotic size, systematically associated with a reduction of the biomass of large individuals (Fig. 6).

System driven by cannibalism show an increasing reduction of fish density with increasing asymptotic size (Fig. 6). Furthermore, small species (e.g., asymptotic size of 10 g) are not affected by cannibalism (Fig. 6A and B). Fishing pressure reduces cannibalism pressure (e.g., (Fig. 6D) associated with an increase of intermediary size biomass (Fig. 6C; dotted-lines, around 10^2 g). The fishing effect on the spectrum seems to increase for large species with asymptotic size of 10^6 g, with a strong increase of medium size biomass (Fig. 6E; dotted-lines).

Systems driven by competition show an increasing feeding reduction with asymptotic size (Fig. 6B, D, and F), leading to an increasing competition intensity. The competition effect of reducing feeding is decreased by Fishing, however this effect is higher for large species (e.g., asymptotic size of 10^6 g; (Fig. 6F). The positive effect of fishing on competition is observed on the population spectrum through increasing biomass of medium size (e.g., between 10^4 and 10^5 g for a population asymptotic size of 10^6 g; Fig. 6E).

3.2 Effect of density dependence on the fishing selection response

The selection response of the size at maturation w_m is decreasing with increasing fishing intensity for the three kinds of density dependence (Fig. 7A). By contrast, in the case of competition for resource (i.e., low resource condition) the strength of the selection response is lower than for other types of density dependence (early-life density dependence and canni-

Figure 6: POPULATION SPECTRUM OVER INCREASING ASYMPTOTIC SIZE UNDER FISHING VERSUS NO FISHING. The Population spectrum (A, C and E) and feeding and loss (B, D, and F) are obtained for fishing ($F = 0.3$; dark grey areas) and no fishing ($F = 0$; light grey areas), and for asymptotic size of 10, 10^4 , and 10^6 g. The three density dependent conditions are represented for each asymptotic size and fishing intensity. The vertical black dotted-line represents the size at maturation. Other parameters are presented in Tab. 1

balism). Systems driven by both early-life density dependence and cannibalism show similar selection responses over fishing. When the dominant density dependence is either early-life

Figure 7: SELECTION RESPONSE OVER FISHING AND ASYMPTOTIC SIZE FOR THE THREE KINDS OF DENSITY DEPENDENCE. A. Selection response over increasing fishing from 0 to 1 year⁻¹. The population asymptotic size was fixed at 10³ g. B. Selection response over increasing size at maturation from 10 to 10⁶ g. The maximum fishing F was fixed at 0.3 year⁻¹. DD represents the "Density dependence".

density dependence or cannibalism the strength of the selection response increases from 0 to -1.5 year⁻¹ for increasing fishing intensity from 0 to 1 year⁻¹, respectively. When the dominant density dependence is competition, the strength of the selection response increases from 0 to -1.2 year⁻¹ for increasing fishing intensity variation from 0 to 1 year⁻¹, respectively.

The selection response of size at maturation over asymptotic size (W_∞), with a fishing of 0.3 year⁻¹, shows different trends, depending on the type of density dependence (Fig. 7B). Selection responses associated with early-life density dependence and cannibalism decrease with asymptotic size. However, cannibalism is associated with a lower strength of selection than early-life density dependence (the selection response is respectively of -4.5 and -5 year⁻¹ for an asymptotic size of 10⁶ g). When competition dominates the system, the trend of the selection response on size at maturation is changing over asymptotic size. The strength of the selection increases (selection response varies from -0.5 to -5 10⁻⁴ year⁻¹ for increasing asymptotic size from 10² to 10⁴ g respectively), then decreases (selection response varies from -5 to -3.8 10⁻⁴ year⁻¹ for increasing asymptotic size from 10⁴ to 10⁶ g respectively).

4 Discussion

This study has provided an understanding of how fishing induced evolution changes by accounting different types of density dependence (i.e., early-life density dependence, density dependent growth, and cannibalism). For intensive fishing pressures, the governance of competition in the system leads to slower evolution than systems driven by cannibalism or early-life density dependence. The model shows for low resource conditions and for both large and small species a slow evolution, while medium species suffer faster evolution. Moreover, cannibalism tends, for large species, to reduce fishing induced evolution compared to a population only driven by early-life density dependence.

Former studies have mainly considered density dependence through a stock recruitment function (Beverton and Holt, 1957), assuming a constant growth rate. A study from Andersen and Brander (2009), considering a constant growth rate, has shown that the selection response to fishing on size at maturation was expected to linearly decrease with increasing fishing and increasing asymptotic size. In this study, conditions of early-life density dependence leads to a constant growth (i.e., feeding of 0.6), and succeeded to reproduce the trend of selection response expected by Andersen and Brander (2009). However, the strength of selection expected in their study is lower than expected by this model (selection response of 0 year^{-1} for their study, and of $0.3 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ in this study, for a fishing pressure of 0.2 year^{-1}), suggesting that effort should be done to evaluate both heritability and the coefficient of variation of size at maturation (see Eq. 24), which were arbitrarily fixed at 0.2.

Compared to early-life density dependence, cannibalism is rarely represented in marine fish models, whilst models of fish populations in lakes are more likely to consider density dependence later in life. Indeed, this study have shown that cannibalism and early-life density dependence provide a similar selection response to fishing pressures when relatively small species are considered. In contrast, considering large species, the strength of selection due to cannibalism is expected to be lower than that expected from early-life density dependence, suggesting that assumption of early density-dependent regulation could be challenged. Indeed This contrast of selection in large species could be explained at the population scale. The model shows increasing cannibalism effect on the population with increasing asymptotic size. Cannibalism effect occurs through increasing mortality from large individuals in the population, tending to reduce smaller individual biomass. Fishing reduces cannibalism effect, or at

least changes the population structure by increasing medium size biomass. Fishing provides negative effects as well as positive effects on the population. The general effect of decreasing population fitness is then expected to be balanced by reducing negative cannibalism effect.

Density dependent growth, for high fishing pressure, induces less evolution than other types of density dependence. High fishing pressures are associated with a strong reduction of the strength of competition. Meaning that negative effects of density dependence on the ecology of populations are partly removed by harvesting large fish. Indeed, reduction of large individual biomass due to fishing on the population is lower for high density dependence growth. As developed before, these results suggest that both negative and positive effect are induced by fishing in systems driven by competition, leading to a decrease of the strength of evolution. For large species, competition pressure is higher than for lower species. Fishing effect has been found to reduce strongly competition of large species, leading to increasing biomass of medium size. As we explained before, fishing is expected to reduce competition pressure, leading to slow evolution. However, this study does not provide clear interpretation of higher selection response for medium asymptotic size and lower selection response for small species.

Effect of density-dependent growth has already been founded to effect fishing induced evolution assessment. Eikeset et al. (2016) have studied the effect of the assumption of high density-dependence growth (i.e., high competition) to reproduce 74 years of data on length at maturation of the northeast Arctic cod. When weak competition is assumed, their model did not perform to reproduce historical data without evolution on length at maturation. While high competition is assumed, their model performs best to reproduce data with low coefficient of variation (i.e., little fisheries-induced evolution). These results suggest that more evolution is required to explain maturation trends when density dependence of growth is weak. An explanation is provided by this study, suggesting that density-dependent growth for cod (asymptotic size of $2 \cdot 10^4$ g from Beverton and Holt (1957)) could result in more intense initial evolution.

Do not consider cannibalism seems a fair assumption since it does not effect the selection response until large species. In contrast, do not consider density dependent growth could lead to strong errors in the assessment of the level of fishing induced evolution, however,

this model is subject to limitations. Firstly, this model is not specific to a species or a location, and parameters used are obtained by averaging data from various places and species. Moreover there is a strong variability among species, for instance, β was evaluated at 480 in average but is equal to 100 for Cod and 1000 Dab (Ursin, 1973). The impact of parameters variability on the result remains unknown. Results could change for a particular species. A way to assess parameters impact could be to randomly choose the parameters in a law of distribution in order to evaluate the possible range of results. A second strong assumption in the model is that resource is assumed to regenerate with a constant factor r_0 over size. This assumption is obviously false, because resource is expected to strongly change with size over time, but there is no proper evaluation of the resource at large scale.

Studies on fishing induced evolution generally focus on three types of life history traits, size at maturation, investment in growth rate and reproduction (Eikeset et al., 2016; Andersen and Brander, 2009; Dunlop et al., 2009). These life history traits are commonly reported due to their consequences on population dynamics, stock biomass and population recovery. A missing part in our study, is the lack of understanding addressed on how density dependence affects evolution of growth rate and resource investment. These theoretical works generally report an increasing of growth rate and reproduction investment. In our model, competition decreases resource consequently reducing both growth rate and reproduction. Fishing is therefore expected to provide a positive effect on the population through reduction of large individuals biomass associated to increasing resource per capita. Fishing has therefore, a positive effect on growth rate and reproduction, expected to lead to less evolution.

5 Conclusion

This study has shown that the type of density dependence affects fishing induced evolution on size at maturation. The model used reproduces former results assuming constant growth. Comparatively to models assuming only early-life density dependence, cannibalism was found to poorly reduce the rate of evolution, excepted for very large species, and competition is expected to strongly reduced rate of fishing induced evolution for large or small species, and for high fishing intensity. These results are roughly explained by a reduction of negative effects

of both cannibalism and competition, induced by fishing. Further works should be done to assess the impact of density dependence on other life history traits, such as investment in growth rate and reproduction. Accurate assessment of fishing induced evolution is a subject of importance to understand the relative part played by both evolution and phenotypic plasticity; leading to strong impact on population recovery. Therefore, it is important to integrate density dependent growth in models assessing fishing induced evolution.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Equations

Consumer-resource model

Consumption

Size preference $\phi(w, w_p) = \exp \left[\frac{-(\ln(w/\beta w_p))^2}{2\sigma^2} \right]$

Encountered food $E_e(w) = \gamma w^q \int_0^\infty (N_{\text{res}}(w_p) + N(w_p)) w_p \phi(w_p/w) dw_p$

Maximum consumption $C_{\text{max}}(w) = hw^n$

Feeding $f(w) = \frac{E_e(w)}{E_e(w) + hw^n}$

Growth and Reproduction

Available food $E_a(w) = \epsilon_a (f(w) - f_c) hw^n$

Maturation $\Psi(w) = [1 + (w/\eta W_\infty)^{-u}]^{-1}$

Growth $g(w) = E_a(w) \left[1 - \Psi(w/w_m) \left(\frac{w}{W_\infty} \right)^{(1-n)} \right]$

Reproduction $R_{\text{egg}}(w) = \epsilon_{\text{egg}} E_a(w) \Psi(w/w_m) \left(\frac{w}{W_\infty} \right)^{(1-n)}$

Reproductive output $R_p = \epsilon_R \int_{w_0}^{W_\infty} R_{\text{egg}}(w) N(w) dw$

Mortality

Predation mortality $\mu_p(w_p) = \int_0^\infty \frac{\phi(w_p/w) f(w) hw^n N(w)}{E(w)} dw$

Background mortality $\mu_b(w) = \mu_0 w^{n-1}$

Fishing mortality $\mu_F(w) = F(1 + (w/\eta_F W_\infty)^{-u_0})^{-1}$

Total mortality $\mu(w) = \mu_p(w) + \mu_b + \mu_F(w)$

Dynamics

Resource dynamics $\frac{dN_{\text{res}}(w)}{dt} = r_0 w^{n-1} (k_{\text{res}}(w) - N_{\text{res}}(w)) - \mu_p(w) N_{\text{res}}(w)$

Carrying capacity $k_{\text{res}}(w) = k_{\text{res}0} w^{-2-q+n}$

Population dynamics $\frac{\partial N(w,t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial g(w)N(w,t)}{\partial w} = -\mu(w)N(w,t)$

Evolution

Spawning stock biomass $B_{\text{SSB}} = \int_{w_0}^{w_\infty} N(w)\phi(w)w dw$

Selection response $S = h^2 (Cv w_{\text{m, res}})^2 \frac{1}{w_{\text{m, res}}} \left. \frac{dr}{dw_{\text{m}}} \right|_{w_{\text{m}}=w_{\text{m, res}}}$

Slope of invasion fitness $\frac{dr}{dw_{\text{m, ivd}}} = \frac{r(w_{\text{m, res}}) - r(w_{\text{m, ivd}})}{w_{\text{m, res}} - w_{\text{m, ivd}}}$

Appendix B

Spectrum discretization

POPULATION SPECTRUM

The population spectrum (Eq. 16) has to be solved to calculate the predation function and consequently the growth and reproduction. The numerical solution was developed by Andersen et al. (2016). The function is discretized over a logarithmic body size scale with the formula: $w_j = (1 + c_{\text{exp}})w_{j-1}$. The factor c_{exp} determines the expansion of the body size. For the sake of simplicity, the notations were simplified in such a way that, $N_j^t = N(w_j, t)$, $g_j^t = g(w_j, t)$ and $\mu_j^t = \mu(j, t)$. Eq. 16 can now be rewritten as follows:

$$\frac{N_j^{t+1} - N_j^t}{\Delta t} + \frac{g_j^t N_j^{t+1} - g_{j-1}^t N_{j-1}^t}{\Delta w_j} = -\mu_j^t N_j^{t+1},$$

where, $\Delta w_j = w_j - w_{j-1}$ is the body size scale and $\Delta t = 0.1 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ is the time scale. Gathering terms of N_j and N_{j-1} gives:

$$N_j^t = N_{j-1}^{t+1} \left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\Delta w_j} g_{j-1}^t \right) + N_j^{t+1} \left(1 + \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta w_j} g_j^t + \Delta t \mu_j^t \right).$$

We define $A_j = \left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\Delta w_j} g_{j-1}^t \right)$ and $B_j = \left(1 + \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta w_j} g_j^t + \Delta t \mu_j^t \right)$. Now we can rewrite the last equation as a recursive function:

$$N_j^{t+1} = \frac{N_j^t - A_j N_{j-1}^{t+1}}{B_j}.$$

Since the number of individual of size j at a given time t (N_j^t) depends on the number of individual at the previous size $j - 1$ (N_{j-1}^t), we need to introduce an initial condition N_0^t . This initial condition, also called the boundary condition, is the number of individual at the first size R (Eq. 11 and 10).

RESOURCE SPECTRUM

The numerical solution of the resource spectrum (Eq. 17) is obtained by discretizing the function over a time step $\Delta t = 0.1 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and over a size step Δw which increases as a

logarithmic function (as explained above). By discretizing Eq. 17 we obtain:

$$\frac{N_{res,j}^{t+1} - N_{res,j}^t}{\Delta t} = r_0 w_{j,t}^{n-1} (k_{res,j}^t - N_{res,j}^{t+1}) - \mu_{p,j}^t N_{res,j}^{t+1}.$$

Gathering the different factors we have:

$$N_j^{t+1} (1 + \Delta t r_0 w_j^{n-1} + \Delta t \mu_{p,j}) = \Delta t r_0 w_{j,t}^{n-1} k_{res,j} + N_j^t.$$

Finally, we get the following recursive formula:

$$N_{res,j}^{t+1} = \frac{\Delta t r_0 w_{j,t}^{n-1} k_{res,j} + N_j^t}{A},$$

with $A = 1 + \Delta t r_0 w_j^{n-1} + \Delta t \mu_{p,j}$ and $k_{res}(w) = k_{res0} w^{-2-q-n}$.

Summary

Fish stocks currently experience a high mortality caused by intensive fishing. A high selection pressure is supported by large individuals, leading to evolution on life history traits such as size at maturation, growth rate, and reproduction. Until recently, density dependence was mainly assumed to occur only in early life, and no systematic efforts were done to explore the role of late density dependence on fish population models. We explored in this study how the type of density dependence affects fishing-induced evolution assessment on size at maturation. Through a size-based model of fish populations we made evolutionary impact assessment under three kinds of density dependence (early-life density dependence, competition for resource, and cannibalism). This study has revealed that the type of density dependence is expected to affect the rate of initial evolution. The strength of initial fishing induced evolution appears to be deeply reduced for systems governed by resource competition. Whereas systems driven by cannibalism or early-life density dependence are roughly similar. It is therefore necessary to explicitly represent density dependent growth to accurately assess rates of fishing induced evolution.

Résumé

Les réserves de poissons supportent actuellement de fort taux de mortalité causés par la pêche intensive. Il en résulte une pression de sélection sur les individus de grandes tailles, conduisant à une évolution sur les traits d'histoire de vie tels que la taille à maturité sexuelle, le taux de croissance, ou la reproduction. Jusqu'à présent une grande partie des modèles prédisant l'évolution induite par la pêche supposaient que la densité dépendance intervenait uniquement au début de la vie. Cette étude a permis d'explorer l'impact d'autres types de densité dépendance, plus tardifs, sur l'évolution induite par la pêche. Les calculs d'évolutions ont été produit par sur un modèle basé sur la taille individuelle, gouverné par trois types de densité dépendances: le cannibalisme, la compétition, et la densité dépendance au début de la vie. Nous avons principalement montré que la compétition pour la ressource affecte fortement la force initiale de l'évolution induite par la pêche comparativement aux autres types de densité dépendances. L'évaluation de l'impact évolutif de la pêche doit plus largement prendre en compte le type de densité dépendance gouvernant les populations surveillées.